

CREATIVE INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGIES, MODELS AND METHODS FOR LANGUAGE LEARNERS

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Abstract: *This study is intended to provide a brief overview of creative strategies and modules for English language learners, so we offered higher education students and senior students their experiences and insights on this topic. The design of this study is qualitative-descriptive and analytical, which makes it easy to understand the importance of creativity and ways of promoting new ideas in a foreign or selected language. In addition, the main purpose of this article is to determine the importance of introducing new ideas in language and speech. In other words, it summarizes a number of proven complex strategies that illustrate how to take a positive approach to common problems in this sphere.*

Keywords: *creativity, models, strategies, critical thinking, peer interaction, problem solving and reflective skills, new ideas.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu tadqiqot ingliz tili o‘rganuvchilari uchun yaratuvchanlik strategiyalari va modullari haqida qisqacha ma‘lumot berishga mo‘ljallangan, shu tufayli oliy ta‘lim talabalari va yuqori bosqichdagi o‘quvchilarga bu mavzu doirasida olib borilgan tajriba va qarashlarni taklif qildik. Ushbu tadqiqotning dizayni sifatlash-tavsifiy va analitik bo‘lib, u chet yoki tanlangan tilda yaratuvchanlik va yangicha fikrlarni targ‘ib qilishning usullari ahamiyatini oson tushunishga imkon beradi. Bundan tashqari, ushbu maqolaning asosiy maqsadi tilda va nutqda yangi g‘oyalarni olib kirish qanday ahamiyatga ega bo‘lish ehtimolligini aniqlashdir. Boshqa so‘z bilan aytganda, bir nechta isbotlangan murakkab strategiyalarni jamlash orqali ushbu sohadagi umumiy muammolarga qanday ijobiy yondashish kerakligi tasvirlanadi.*

Аннотация: *Это исследование предназначено для предоставления краткого обзора творческих стратегий и модулей для изучающих английский язык, поэтому мы предложили студентам высших учебных заведений и старшеклассникам их опыт и идеи по этой теме. Дизайн этого исследования носит качественно-описательный и аналитический характер, что позволяет легко понять важность творчества и способов продвижения новых идей на иностранном или выбранном языке. Кроме того, основной целью данной статьи является определение важности внедрения новых идей в язык и речь. Другими словами, в нем обобщается ряд проверенных комплексных стратегий, которые иллюстрируют позитивный подход к общим проблемам в этой области.*

Introduction:

"Creativity is seeing what others see and thinking what no one else ever thought" - Albert Einstein. Creative thinking or merely coming up with diverse ideas are crucial parts of producing language. Teaching language within the assistance of creative strategies can enhance students to learn the language with different models and methods. Intermediate level students are able to take responsibility of their own learning, working independently, doing self-study with the existing approaches. Introducing creative modules enables students to think in alternative ways towards traditional learning system. This study aimed to evolve benefits of a creative teaching method as a learning strategy.

According to Ben Johnson, administrator and author of the book `Teaching Students to Dig Deeper`, there are 4 main strategies for teaching students how to think creatively and making exercises and activities in this field. In this research he mentioned some tips including: 1. Setting up different activities allowing students to use their creativity in relevant, interesting and worthwhile ways; 2. To value creativity and reward it; 3. Teaching students skills that can be useful for being creative; 4. Declining usage of limited activities, giving students space for feeling themselves free and creative.

The main findings, personal analyses and results:

Many psychologists and educators argue that creativity skills are necessary for success in school and in the future workforce. As a result, schools have a responsibility to teach and value them. According to one 2010 survey, over 1,500 executives regarded creativity as the most important business skill in the modern world. In a knowledge economy where machines can perform rote tasks and almost all information is available with a single click, students must be prepared to learn independently and constantly adapt, innovate, and problem-solve creatively in the workplace.

Creativity also improves learning directly by increasing motivation, deepening understanding, and promoting joy. Intrinsic motivation is critical to the creative process, and it is dependent on students pursuing meaningful goals. Creative thinking, which is at the top of Bloom's taxonomy, can facilitate deeper cross-curricular learning by noticing broader patterns and connecting material across academic disciplines. The strategies that support creativity solving problems, exploring multiple options, and learning inquiry also support depth of understanding, as Alane Jordan Starko points out in her book *Creativity in the Classroom*.

She also states that the percentage and levels of creativity decreases with aging of the human brain. In other words, children have more brain capacity with brilliant ideas and diverse thoughts. They always have different opinion towards one thing. Training students from the early ages is the ine easiest way for improving their creativity. Opinion based or giving group works can be suggestive and efficient way for teachers. However it is different with adult students, since they are more aware of their thoughts and have already passed to period of taking responsibilities. With different activities and giving them drawing or story making projects, teacher enables them to use their creativity.

Giving students a chance to explore their ability in terms of coming up with their own examples and ideas can add some more convenience to the classroom competetiveness and understanding. For instance, implementing creativity based activities in class is the organized way for checking their creativity level. When it comes to assesment, they can be rewarded according to their fantastic fields. It can help students to think broadly and not be honed to the way teacher`s explanation and strategies.

Since it is mentioned earlier, teachers can use 4 strategies improve students creativity skills since it can help them to strangthen their decision making and problem solving skills. Students are more likely to be able to create new things when they have freedom during their classes, but in a limited ways. But with this way it may be somehow problematic since different characters, different students and various ideas always exist, so teacher should be more aware of their behaviour during classes. Moreover, it is important to mention that focus of students shoulod be dragged to the subject within the help of activities, along with enhancing their skills and improving creative skills.

Conclusion

This article attempted to emphasize the significance and assistance of creative instructional strategies and moduls for language learners in terms of all four skills and provide examples within proven experiments, questionnaires adopted from universities which can help to enhance and evolve new ideas and methods for Language Learning. In this area,. In fact, when selecting themes and implementing them in classes, students' interests, intentions, and major fields should be taken into account. Besides, in order to create innovative and creative activities teachers should also have broad horizon, so that they enable their students to work on their creative strategies. Another founding is that as age grows old the probablity of creativity level decreases, so it is better to teach students from the early ages for this will be the

reason having high creativity levels in the future, and it prevents students from having deals with plagiarism.

References:

1. Alane Jordan Starko. Professor in the Department of Teacher Education at Eastern Michigan University, USA, and author of the blog creativiteach.me. A former elementary school teacher, teacher of the gifted, and head of the Teacher Education Department at Eastern Michigan University, she also served on the board of directors of the National Association for Gifted Children.
2. Ben Johnson. Administrator, educator and author of the book `Teaching Students to Dig Deeper`. <https://www.edutopia.org/article/4-ways-develop-creativity-students>
3. https://www.teachingenglish.org.uk/sites/teacheng/files/pub_F004_ELT_Creativity_FINAL_v2%20WEB.pdf
4. <https://www.teachthought.com/pedagogy/101-ways-for-teachers-to-be-more-creative>